

A prospective randomized-controlled trial study comparing Dexmedetomidine Vs Dexamethasone as adjuvant to Levobupivacaine in TAP block for patients undergoing LSCS

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Abstract— Background: Transversus abdominis plane (TAP) block is commonly used to treat post-operative pain after lower abdominal surgeries. The aim of this randomized controlled study was to assess the efficacy of adding Dexmedetomidine Vs Dexamethasone to Levopivacaine in TAP block and compare the two for post-operative pain relief in patients undergoing LSCS.

Methods: A 44 parturient (18–35 years) undergoing LSCS under spinal anesthesia received bilateral TAP block. Group D1 received bilateral TAP block with 18 ml 0.25% Levobupivacaine with 2 ml Inj. Dexamethasone (8mg) on each side, while Group D2 received TAP block with same volume of Levobupivacaine with 0.5µg/ kg of Dexmedetomidine diluted in 2ml of normal saline. In this prospective, randomized, double-blind study, time to initial self-reporting of post-operative pain, time to first rescue analgesic demand, visual analogue scale (VAS) for pain, hemodynamic parameters, and adverse effects if any were noted. P value < 0.05 was considered as statistically significant.

Results: Time to initial self-reporting of post-operative pain (337.6+/-195.2 Vs 410.1+/-142.3, $P= 0.01$) and time to first rescue analgesic (406.9+/-201.2 Vs 473.5+/-152.8, $P=0.03$) were significantly longer in group D2 as compared to group D1. VAS score at the time of completion of surgery, at 4,8,12 hours postoperative period was significantly lower in group D2. No significant hemodynamic changes or side-effects were noted.

Conclusion: Adding Dexmedetomidine to Levobupivacaine as compared with Dexamethasone in bilateral TAP block following LSCS prolongs the time of initial post-operative pain reporting & time to first rescue analgesic consumption.

Keywords— Dexamethasone, Dexmedetomidine, Levobupivacaine, TAP block

I. INTRODUCTION

Pain control post caesarean is very crucial especially during the first 24 hours so that patient can be ambulated early & breast feeding can be established sooner. Usually, multimodal approach is incorporated for postoperative analgesia. Regional nerve blocks like TAP block incorporated as a part of opioid sparing analgesic technique. (1) The accuracy of local anesthetic deposition is enhanced with the help of ultrasound, thereby blocking the sensory nerves more effectively and enhancing the efficacy of analgesia. Various adjuvants like opioids, Ketamine, Dexamethasone, Dexmedetomidine, Clonidine have been utilized successfully in peripheral nerve blocks to enhance the duration of post-operative analgesia (2-4)

II. METHODS

After getting approval from ethical committee (DVVPF's VIMS/IEC/C/2022/68), a prospective, randomized, double blind controlled trial was conducted in period of 6 months. (April 2023- September 2023). Population under study was patients posted for LSCS with ASA grade 2 or 3. Simple random sampling done by computer generated numbers.

Inclusion Criteria-

1. Pregnant women undergoing elective and emergency caesarean sections under spinal anesthesia.
2. Parturient of ASA grade 2 or 3
3. Age between 18 to 35

Exclusion Criteria-

1. The patient's denial
2. Parturient with ASA grade > 3
3. Infection at the site of block.
4. Coagulation or bleeding problems.
5. Patients who were switched to general anesthesia after Spinal anesthesia
6. known hypersensitivity to study drugs under study

After getting written informed consent, all parturient were randomly allocated using computer generated random numbers into two groups. 50 parturient were recruited in this trial, out of which 6 parturient were excluded for not fitting into the study criteria. 44 parturient were allocated into 2 groups of 22 each to receive USG guided TAP block bilaterally with 18 ml 0.25% Levobupivacaine on each side with 2 ml inj. Dexamethasone (8mg) as adjuvant for group D1, while 0.5µg/ kg of Dexmedetomidine diluted in 2ml of normal saline for group D2. All the parturient were made familiar with visual analogue scale (VAS) with 0 representing no pain and 10 representing worst imaginable pain prior to the administration of spinal. All parturient received spinal anesthesia with 0.5% hyperbaric Levobupivacaine 10mg. An USG bilateral TAP block was performed in all the patients at the end of surgery as described earlier. The time of institution of TAP block was taken as time zero and the time from giving of TAP block to the time for first analgesic request in the post-operative period was recorded. Post-operative pain was evaluated using VAS score at 0,4,8,12 hours, Time to initial self-reporting of post-operative pain and time of first rescue analgesic was also recorded. Slow iv injection of Diclofenac sodium 75 mg was administered as first rescue analgesic and continued every 8 hour thereafter. Hemodynamic parameters like NIBP, heart rate, saturation was also noted along with VAS. The study ended once the patient received her first rescue analgesic dose. Data was described in terms of range, mean \pm standard deviation, frequencies (number of cases) and relative frequencies (percentages) as appropriate. Appropriate statistical tests were used & data analyzed using SSPS software. P value <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

III. RESULTS

44 patients were recruited in this study. The mean time to initial self-reporting of post-operative pain was significantly prolonged in D2 group (410.1 \pm 142.3 Vs 337.6 \pm 195.2 minutes, *P* value 0.01). *The mean time to first analgesic requirement when VAS \geq 3 was significantly longer in parturient receiving Dexmedetomidine (473.5 \pm 152.8 min) as compared with those receiving Dexamethasone (406.9 \pm 201.2, *P* value 0.03)* The two groups were comparable with regards to demographic profile and duration of surgery. There was no significant difference in post-operative hemodynamic parameters between the two groups. Hypotension and bradycardia were reported in 13.6% of patients in Dexmedetomidine group.

TABLE 1
COMPARISON OF PARAMETERS UNDER STUDY

Characteristic	Group D1(n=22)	Group D2(n=22)	P value
Age (in years)	24.41+/-4.74	25.68+/-5.44	0.419
Weight (in kg)	66.45+/-6.97	65.23+/-7.44	0.576
Duration of surgery (in minutes)	52.93+/-5.77	52.13+/-6.02	0.657
ASA grade (II/III)	(17/5)	(16/6)	0.65
Self-reporting of pain(in minutes)	337.6+/-195.2	410.1+/-142.3	0.01
Time to first rescue analgesic (in minutes)	406.9+/-201.2	473.5+/-152.8	0.03

TABLE 2
Intraoperative and post operative complications

Complication	Group D1(n=22)	Group D2(n=22)	Statistical test	P value
Hypotension	0(0%)	3 (13.6%)	Fischer's exact test	0.48
Bradycardia	0 (0%)	3 (13.6%)	Fischer's exact test	0.48
Hypertension	5 (22.7%)	0 (0%)	Fischer's exact test	0.22
Tachycardia	3 (13.6%)	0 (0%)	Fischer's exact test	0.48
Nausea & vomiting	3 (13.6%)	9 (40%)	Fischer's exact test	0.21
Urine retention	0 (0%)	3 (13.6%)	Fischer's exact test	0.48
VAS SCORE (mean+/- S.D.)				
Completion of surgery	3.13+/-0.91	1.13+/-0.51	Mann Whitney U test=4.58	<0.01
4 hours postoperatively	2.93+/-0.70	1.20+/-0.86	Mann Whitney U test=4.13	<0.01
8 hours postoperatively	2.47+/-0.64	1.20+/-0.67	Mann Whitney U test=3.99	<0.01
12 hours postoperatively	2.33+/-0.48	1.6+/-0.73	Mann Whitney U test=2.83	<0.01

IV. DISCUSSION

Post-operative caesarean section pain is mainly because of somatic pain due to surgical incision and visceral pain due to inflammation. TAP block inhibits the neural afferents from T7-L1 leading to somatic pain antagonism. It is a multifaceted block.

The anterior rami of the T7-L1 nerves provide sensation to skin, muscles & parietal peritoneum of the anterior abdominal wall. After exiting the vertebral column’s foramina, these nerves pass through the lateral abdominal wall within the fascial plane between the internal oblique & transversus abdominis muscles. Injecting local anesthetic into this fascial plane produces TAP block. (6) It involves a single bolus injection of LA (local anesthetic) into this fascial plane between internal oblique & transversus abdominis muscle. The prolonged duration of analgesia after TAP block may be because this plane is relatively poorly vascularized, making drug clearance slow by reduction of absorption in to the blood stream and decreasing risk of systemic toxicity from the LA.

Under USG guidance the block is given in supine position after the completion of surgery. A linear array high frequency probe (6-13 MHz) is used. After aseptic skin preparation & draping, the ultrasound probe is placed just superior to the iliac crest in the mid axillary line, oriented transversely to the abdomen. The 3 abdominal muscle layers are identified. A 2 inch, 24-gauge, blunt regional anesthesia needle is introduced within the plane of ultrasound probe & maneuvered. The needle is advanced until the tip lies between the internal oblique & transversus abdominis muscles. After confirming negative aspiration, LA is injected slowly.

Levobupivacaine is the s-isomer of racemic Bupivacaine. It is less cardiotoxic & less neurotoxic. It is equally potent LA compared to its racemate. It is known to cause less depression of myocardial contractility.

Dexamethasone produces analgesia through its anti-inflammatory or immunosuppressive action. It potentiates the action of local anesthetic through modulation of function of the potassium channels. Neuroprotection and anti-hyperalgesia effects with clinically relevant dosing of perineural Dexamethasone along with LA have also been studied.

Dexmedetomidine is a highly selective central alpha-2 adrenergic agonist. Dexmedetomidine when used via epidural route has synergistic effect with Levobupivacaine. (5) It has profound sedative, anxiolytic and analgesic properties which reduces the inflammation and prolongs the duration of nerve block through vasoconstriction and inhibiting hyperpolarization-activated cationic current. Dexmedetomidine acts by blocking the conduction of nerve signals through C & A delta fibers and may stimulate the release of enkephalin-like substances at peripheral sites.

The main results of our study reveal superiority of Dexmedetomidine as an adjuvant to Levobupivacaine in TAP block since it has longer time of initial self-reporting of pain and prolonged mean time to initial rescue analgesic administration. The VAS score at 0,4,8,12 hours was significantly less in D2 group. Also, the mean time to first rescue analgesic administration was prolonged in parturient receiving Dexmedetomidine as an adjuvant compared with those receiving Dexamethasone. Diclofenac sodium (iv) 75mg was used as a rescue analgesic, once the patient complained of pain. The mean time to first rescue analgesic was 67 minutes later in the patients belonging to D2 group as compared with D1 group, which was statistically significant.

Bradycardia and hypotension were recorded in 13.6% of parturient in D2 group. This can be explained by the action of Dexmedetomidine on centrally acting alpha 2A adrenergic receptors, causing decreased release of noradrenaline from the sympathetic nervous system.

V. CONCLUSION

As an adjuvant to Levobupivacaine in TAP block, Dexmedetomidine significantly reduces post operative pain, self-reporting of pain prolongs duration of analgesia and the time to first rescue analgesic as compared with Dexamethasone with minimal adverse effects in parturient undergoing LSCS. Dexmedetomidine provides good hemodynamic stability when used as an adjuvant in TAP block.

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